

MDDPlatform Features and Capabilities

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This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This document introduces MDDPlatform, the microservice-based environment developed for model-driven development. It describes its functionality, including domain definition, decomposition, multi-level modeling, hierarchical model structures, transformation patterns, and executable processes. The content provides a detailed overview of how the platform supports modeling and code generation.

1. Introduction to MDDPlatform

1.1. Defining the Problem Domain

To apply the model-driven development in MDDPlatform, we first need to define the problem domain.

Figure 1: Defining the problem domain

Figure 2: Display the list of subdomains of the problem domain

1.2. Problem Domain Decomposition

In MDDPlatform, it is possible to break the problem domain and define subdomains.

Figure 3: Problem domain decomposition

Figure 4: List of subdomains defined in the problem domain

1.3. Definition of Different Levels of Modeling

Multiple models can be created at different levels of abstraction to describe each subdomain from different perspective

Figure 5: Defining a model, at a specific abstraction level and based on a specific metamodel

Figure 6: Models defined at different levels of abstraction to describe the Orders subdomain

Table 1: Levels of modeling in the experiment

Name	Type	Tag	Sublevel	Language- version
01- Orders – CRAC Model	CIM	CRAC	1	CRAC Metamodel – 2.0.0
02- Orders – CIM Model	CIM	CIM	1	CIM Metamodel – 2.0.0
03- Orders – CIM Concepts	CIM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
04- Orders – CQRS Model	PIM	CQRS	1	CQRS – 2.0.0
05- Orders – CQRS Concepts	PIM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
06- Orders – Controller Model	PIM	Controller	1	Api Controllers – 2.0.0
07- Orders – Controller Concepts	PIM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
08- Orders – Core Domain Model	PIM	CoreDomain	1	Core Domain – 2.0.0
09- Orders – Core Domain Concepts	PIM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
10- Orders – CQRS Classes	PSM	Classes	1	Classes & Interfaces – 2.0.0
11- Orders – CQRS Class Concepts	PSM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
12- Orders – Controller Classes	PSM	Classes	1	Classes & Interfaces – 2.0.0
13- Orders – Controller Class Concepts	PSM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
14- Orders – Core Domain Classes	PSM	Classes	1	Classes & Interfaces – 2.0.0
15- Orders – Core Domain Class Concepts	PSM	Built-in	1	BaseConcept (Built-in) – 2.0.0
16- Orders – Project Settings & Dependencies	Code	.Net Core	1	.Net Core Project – 2.0.0
17- Orders – Project Files - Classes	Code	Code	1	Project Code Metamodel
18- Orders – Project Files - Interfaces	Code	Code	1	Project Code Metamodel
19- Orders – Project Solution	Code	Code	1	Project Code Metamodel

1.4. Hierarchical Structure to Describe the Model

In MDDPlatform, it is possible to view the constituent elements of the model in the form of a hierarchical structure of domain concepts, instances of each concept (domain objects), and their properties and relations. It is also possible to define new domain objects, as well as edit and delete existing ones. For example, in Figure 7 and Figure 8, you can see the domain concepts and domain objects of a domain model that conforms to the CRAC metamodel.

Figure 7: Modeling language concepts

Figure 8: instances of each concept (domain objects)

1.5. Model Transformation Patterns

In MDDPlatform, model transformations are defined as patterns and provided as services. Similar to design patterns, transformation patterns have a specific purpose and goal. Each transformation pattern requires a set of information defined as pattern parameters to achieve its goals. To perform a transformation operation, these parameters need to be initialized with values, which can be input or output model types, concepts, features of a concept, or relationships between concepts in input or output models.

Since transformation patterns are provided as services, executing a model transformation pattern is equivalent to calling the corresponding service, and initializing pattern parameters is equivalent to initializing the parameters of a service call. Model transformations in MDDPlatform are presented at three levels of abstraction:

1. Transformation Pattern
2. Pattern Instance
3. Pattern Instance Template

Transformation patterns are defined at the highest level of abstraction and have no explicit dependency on input and output metamodels. By initializing all pattern parameters, an instance of the pattern can be created that can be executed, and as a result, the desired changes to the output model are applied. The pattern instance is at the lowest level of abstraction.

Sometimes, the values set for the parameters of a transformation pattern can also be useful and applicable for other issues and projects, regardless of the input and output model. Therefore, based on an instance of a pattern, a template can be created that only has the parameters related to its

input and output models uninitialized, and other pattern parameters have values similar to the pattern instance. Templates created from pattern instances can also be used in other projects. To execute a pattern instance template, only the parameters related to the input and output models need to be configured. The configuration of tasks created from these templates will be discussed in the following sections.

Figure 9 shows a list of model transformation patterns in different categories. To create an instance from each pattern, click on the pattern title link to be directed to the page for creating an instance of that pattern. For example, selecting the ‘ReplaceRelationWithAction’ pattern leads us to the page shown in Figure 10. The parameters of this pattern are shown in this figure. To define an instance of the pattern, we must initialize these parameters. This is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 9: List of Transformation Patterns in MDDPlatform

Figure 10: Create an instance of a pattern (Pattern Instance) by setting its parameters

Figure 11: Set the values of parameters according to the input and output models

After defining a pattern instance, the list of pattern instances is updated, and the new pattern instance is displayed to the user. By selecting a pattern instance, the user is directed to the page shown in Figure 12, where they can view the details of the pattern instance and also execute it. The user can create a template based on this pattern instance. To do this, they click on the link

displayed at the top of the page, called ‘Create Pattern Instance Component’, to be directed to the page shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: A pattern instance details

Figure 13: Create a template (Pattern Instance Template) from a pattern instance

On this page, they can only modify the title and name of the template. Other parameters are determined based on the values of the pattern instance and are not configurable. Parameters related to input and output models are also without values and will be configurable at runtime. Figure 14 shows the details of the template defined from the pattern instance.

Figure 14: The details of a pattern instance templates

1.6. Process Definition

The definition of the process takes place in several steps. First, we specify the title of the process and create it.

Figure 15: Create a process

Then, to define the constituent phases, we select the desired process from the displayed list to be directed to the corresponding page.

Figure 16: List of defined processes

On this page, we define the phases of the process.

Figure 17: Defining the phases of a process and the list of defined phases

To define the activities of a phase, we select the desired phase from the list of defined phases to be directed to the activity definition page. There are two ways to define the activity. In the first method, we define the activity using the information of a Pipeline. In MDDPlatform, a concept called Pipeline has been defined, which is equivalent to a chain of transformation patterns that, by executing it, transformations are executed one after the other. By executing the last item of this chain, the Pipeline execution ends successfully. It is possible to define manual tasks among the chain of transformation patterns. If such a task exists, Pipeline execution will stop until the manual task is completed successfully. We may also encounter errors during conversions. In this case, the execution of Pipeline will be stopped. After removing the possible obstacles, the Pipeline can be continued or it can be restarted. In the second method, we only define the title of the activity at this stage. Next, by selecting that activity, we will be directed to the task definition page to define the tasks that make up that activity.

Figure 18: Define an activity

Figure 19: The list of defined activities (in this example, the activities defined in the Inception phase)

Currently, two types of tasks can be defined in MDDPlatform. The first type is manual tasks. We may need to enter information (refine a model) during the MDD process. This step is defined as manual tasks. Figure 20 shows how to add a manual task.

Figure 20: Defining the tasks that make up an activity - manual task definition

Another type of tasks are automated tasks, which correspond to a transformation pattern that can be executed automatically after the process is configured. Automated tasks are defined based on templates created from pattern instances. Figure 21 shows how to define automatic tasks.

Figure 21: Defining the tasks that make up an activity - automatic task definition

Figure 22: Tasks constituting an activity

Figure 23: List of processes defined for the experiment

Figure 24: Details of a MDD process

1.7. Process Configuration

In MDDPlatform, the model-driven development process includes manual and automated tasks. Automated tasks in MDDPlatform correspond to executing model transformations. Each of these transformations can transform one or more input models to one or more output models. Therefore, the process configuration is equivalent to specifying the input and output models for each of the automated tasks (Pattern Instance Template).

Figure 25: MDD process configuration

After configuring all these tasks, we click on the "Create Executable Process" button at the end of this page to create an executable process by combining the process information and configuration data.

Figure 26: Automatic task (Model transformation) configuration

1.8. Process Execution

After creating an executable process, it can be started. When the process is executed, automated tasks automatically execute model transformations one after another. Upon successful completion of each transformation, the task status is automatically set to "Done". When a manual task is reached, the process execution is paused and the user is asked to perform the relevant task (e.g. refine the model). After completing the task, the user can click the "Done" button and then request to continue the process execution. Upon completion of the last task in this process, the process execution ends successfully.

Figure 27: Running a process

1.9. Scripts

During the execution of the process of creating a model runner, it may be necessary to manually enter some information. This can be done in two ways. In the usual method, the model information can be viewed and actions can be taken to create, edit, or delete instances through the graphical interface provided. The second method is to define and save the desired changes to the model using a set of commands in the form of a script. By running this script, the desired changes are applied to the model.

Figure 28: Script Editor

Figure 29: Instructions code

Figure 30: Scripts management

1.10. Download Project Code

After executing the code generation process from the model, it is possible to receive the solution code in the form of a Zip file.

Figure 31: Download the solution code